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Report on **Milestone 34**

Expose ESS' interoperable services to external consumers

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Abstract:

Milestone 34, “Expose ESS' interoperable services to external consumers”, was achieved on 17 December 2022. It completes the new data infrastructure of the ESS survey.

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1. Introduction

Milestone 34, Expose ESS' interoperable services to external consumers, was achieved on 17 December 2021. The new system gives users access to the data catalogue of the European Social Survey (ESS) from the new data and metadata repositories via <https://ess-search.nsd.no/en/all/query/>.

2. Description of the Milestone

The data catalogue of the European Social Survey (ESS) can be accessed at <https://ess-search.nsd.no/en/all/query/>. Data and metadata are provided from the new repositories. The architecture of the underlying infrastructures allows users to query the API in a range of ways. Increased use of controlled vocabularies and easier log in (authentication) has given simpler retrieval of data.

The new ESS data and metadata service consists of a network of data and metadata repositories connected by a series of APIs for management and dissemination of the ESS data and metadata. The APIs are effective tools for organizing the storage and dissemination of ESS data and metadata. The system interconnects existing and new infrastructures and is based on the Colectica platform for metadata management.

System Design

Figure 1 (below) shows how the data and documentation is organized at various stages in the process. The red and grey elements illustrate components that lie outside of the SSHOC 5.5 Task (Preparing cross national survey data for the EOOSC. ESS pilot/use case). However, as they are important in understanding the structure of the data storage and API solutions developed within the task, they have been included.

Figure 1: System design of the complete data management system of ESS from data ingest to data dissemination.

Architecture

The architecture allows users to query the API in a range of ways. Increased use of controlled vocabularies and easier log in (authentication) has given simpler retrieval of data. Furthermore, the APIs allow data curators to process, document and publish data and metadata in a secure and stable environment.

The main components of the architecture as shown in Figure 2 include:

- Azure storage for data storage
- Azure Machine Learning service to host Jupyter notebooks and data processing libraries
- Colectica repository to store metadata in DDI-L standard
- Colectica Designer (desktop tool) to curate metadata in DD-L standard
- Colectica workflow to publish metadata
- Metadata Transformer for formatting metadata for consumption by other services
- SurveyStatEngine for analysis and visualisation
- Graphql API to enable access to data and metadata by machines/services.
- Single Sign On for easier login

Figure 2: ESS data service architecture

API design

The APIs are deployed under NSD's tenant in Microsoft Azure. They use a modern API language/interface, GraphQL, to express search and other elements. GraphQL is designed to support strong types and offers flexibility for various clients consuming GraphQL APIs. Moreover, GraphQL APIs encourage decoupling of the externally available API and its types and relations from internal implementation details. Decoupling ensures that API consumers are shielded from internal APIs and systems, offering a stable, flexible, and domain centric API likely to outlive many of its internal technological implementations at any given time. The APIs are standardized on GraphQL since 2018 and they run GraphQL in integration with OAuth2/OpenID connect-based authentication solutions and middleware, supporting fine-grained access control where needed. This means that single sign-on is integrated with the GraphQL API,

providing easier access for ESS users. Both the management and dissemination API harvest information directly from the data and metadata repositories.

ESS metadata is accessible via graphql API. The API documentation can be found at <https://docs.nsd.no/>. Please contact the Task 5.5 team for details.

2.1 Role of the Milestone

MS34 ensures access to the data catalogue of the European Social Survey (ESS) from the new cloud-based data and metadata repositories. Making the ESS metadata and data available via API facilitates reuse by other services. The new search tool allows users to search on detailed metadata within the ESS repository such as the question text or variable names. Users now have access to the rich variable level metadata through the new landing pages. The single sign on has expanded and eased the way users gain access to ESS data. Overall has the FAIRness of the ESS data and service has been greatly increased.

2.2 Means of verification

The means of verification for the milestone is that the interoperable services have been published on the ESS website at <https://ess-search.nsd.no/en/all/query/>. Please see the screenshot below.

Homepage

Figure 3: Screenshot of the new ESS service homepage

Search results

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL <https://ess-search.nsd.no/en/variable/query/benefit/1>. The page header features the European Social Survey logo and a search bar containing the text "benefit". Below the search bar, it indicates "Variables (62) | Studies (0)".

The main content area displays "1 - 10 out of 62 results". The first three results are visible:

- flgvbnf - Falsely claim government benef ... ecurity or other, last 5 years
Studies: ESS2
- sblwcoa - Social benefits/services make ... s willing care for one another
Studies: ESS8
- ubunp - Unemployment benefit if turn down job: refuse unpaid work
Studies: ESS8

The second result, "sblwcoa", is highlighted in a light pink background. Below it is a table with two columns: "Value" and "Category".

Value	Category
1	Agree strongly
2	Agree
3	Neither agree nor disagree
4	Disagree
5	Disagree strongly
7	Refusal
8	Don't know
9	No answer

Below the table are two links: [Go to variable](#) and [Go to study](#).

Figure 4: Screenshot of the search results (variables list) on the new ESS service

Metadata landing pages

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL <https://ess-search.nsd.no/en/study/f8e11f55-0c14-4ab3-abde-96d3f14d3c76>. The page features a red header with the European Social Survey logo and a search bar containing the text "Search for questions, variables and data files in the ESS". Below the header, the main content area is light pink and displays "ESS8-2016". Underneath, it specifies the "Time period: 01-09-2016 - 31-12-2016". A list of sections follows, each with a red downward arrow: "Summary", "Data access", and "Universe, scope and method". A "Data files" section is also present, containing a pink box with the text "ESS8 - integrated file, edition 2.2" and a red "Login to download" button. Below this, there are three more sections with red downward arrows: "Country", "Weights", and "Media and social trust".

Figure 5: Screenshot of the metadata landing page for ESS round 8 on the new ESS service

2.3 Explanation on delay in achieving the Milestone

The work on MS34 was delayed with around three weeks from end November 2021 and was rescheduled for 20 December 2021 due to those parts of the technical work took longer than expected to get in place.

The delay will not affect neither the fulfilment of the task's objectives nor its deliverables.

3. Conclusions and next steps

The achievement of milestone 34 ensures user access to the new services. It completes the new data infrastructure of the ESS survey and supports API-based retrieval of data.

From late January, the services will also be available from the EOSC portal. ESS ERIC registered as service provider in the portal in December 2021, but the SSHOC task 5,5 team has experiences complications in onboarding the service (probably due to the organisational change of the team, please refer to footnote 1).

Remaining deliveries on this task include deliverable reports D5.13 Recommendations for a FAIR compliant integrated data and metadata repository (ESS as a service), and D5.14 Report on preparing the ESS for Services in the EOSC. D5.13 has been peer reviewed and will be submitted according to schedule by 31 January 2022.